

THE IMPORTANCE OF EDUCATIONAL GAMES IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES TO CHILDREN AT AN EARLY AGE

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Annotation: In this article discussed about the importance of educational games in teaching foreign languages to children at an early age

Keywords: educational games, teaching foreign languages, early age, preschool, children, activities.

Introduction. Since the game is the main and favorite activity of the child in kindergarten and school age, the child also discovers the world through the game. If foreign languages are taught in a playful way, this will increase the efficiency of learning language skills several times. The game not only increases the physical activity of the child, but also helps to form mental freshness. The game helps the child to strengthen his self-confidence and to form social relations with others. Therefore, parents and educators should encourage children to learn through play as much as possible. It is through play that children learn and discover their talents. To achieve this, it is considered appropriate to use an environment that activates the senses, including visual, auditory, and kinesthetic types of active education. Educational games include playing musical instruments, singing songs, reciting poems, dancing, playing games, watching videos, and making various crafts.

Discussion. At what age is it better to learn foreign languages? Scientists of the world have expressed a unanimous opinion that a child under the age of 10 can learn a foreign language easily. During this period, the child learns languages not by understanding, but mechanically, so the usage and pronunciation of a foreign language is easily mastered. However, considering that a child is born with the ability to imitate the sounds of any language, there are many people who think of starting this process earlier. As a result of the research on the study of the human brain, it has been proven that the period from the birth of a baby to the age of three is the most important period of child development. [3.14] It has also been found that the brain of a three-year-old child works twice as fast and better than the brain of an adult. Therefore, according to English experts, introducing a second language to a child in the first year will help him learn it easily. But in any case, we must not forget that taking into account the child's psychological and language skills is an extremely important factor.

Every child is an individual, naturally, their developmental stages are different from each other. According to psychologists, trying to force a child to speak from an early age or trying to develop him in comparison with his peers in many cases has the opposite effect and leads to bad results. When teaching a foreign language to children of kindergarten and junior school age, it is necessary to take into account psychological and pedagogical features, that is, their curiosity and enthusiasm. It is also necessary to remember that children cannot focus on one type of activity for a long time [6.3]. Parents want their child to be mature in all aspects, and in many cases, without taking into account the child's psychological and physiological readiness, they try to give him assignments in various subjects, teach him a language, or involve him in sports activities. In most cases, when parents fail to achieve the expected results, they try to influence the child by reprimanding the child or comparing him to his peers. But these two

attempts weaken the child's motivation to learn and cause his interest in the surrounding things to fade. The role of parents and educators in preventing such unfortunate situations is incomparable. The game is the easiest and most appropriate way to teach a child to think freely, to increase his curiosity and motivation to explore the environment, to enrich his imagination, and to bring out his creativity. When children play, they put their ideas into practice, test hypotheses, acquire necessary skills, use their imaginations, and explore their worlds [3.3].

A child is very curious by nature and uses all his senses to explore the world around him. Since the game is the main and favorite activity of the child, if the child is introduced to the world and all the necessary knowledge and skills in it through the game, the efficiency of mastering skills will increase several times. The game not only increases the physical activity of the child, but it also helps to form mental freshness. The game helps the child to strengthen his self-confidence and to form social relations with others. Therefore, parents and educators should encourage children to learn through play as much as possible. It is through the game that children learn and discover their talents. To achieve this, it is appropriate to use an environment that activates the senses, including visual, auditory, and kinesthetic types of active education. Educational games include playing musical instruments, singing songs, reciting poems, dancing, playing games, watching videos, and making various crafts. Games such as colorful exhibitions, cards, competitions, role-playing games, making various shapes are one of the most interesting ways to develop children's physical and mental activity [8.3].

Conclusion. Young children learn through their emotions and actions, so learning English should be done through these emotions and actions. Engaging young children in interesting and communicative situations and activities in learning English is a very important factor in acquiring language skills. Although the purpose of the activity is to teach English, it can attract children like a game, and children can get involved in these activities unintentionally, and children learn the foreign language as naturally as their mother tongue. provision is also of special concern.

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